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Vitamin C Controversy

To the Editor:

In his Dec. 26 letter,¹ Dr. Harold S. Diehl states that in my Dec. 15 letter I had failed to mention the following summary of a report of a study by him and two other physicians: “This controlled study yields no indication that either large doses of vitamin C or large doses of vitamins A, B1, B2, C, D and nicotinic acid have any important effect on the number or severity of infections of the upper respiratory tract when administered to young adults who presumably are already on a reasonably adequate diet.”

The foregoing statement would be false if the word “important” were omitted. It is my opinion that Drs. Cowan, Diehl and Baker made an error of judgment in omitting from their summary, which consisted of the single sentence quoted above, any mention of the fact that they had observed a statistically significant decrease of 15 per cent in the incidence of colds in the students who received 200 milligrams of vitamin C a day relative to those who received a placebo.

Dr. Diehl and I agree about the facts. In my letter I quoted the following sentences from the body of the report by Drs. Cowan, Diehl and Baker: “The actual difference between the two groups during the year of the study amounts to one-third of a cold per person. Statistical analysis of the data reveals that a difference as large as this would arise only three or four times in a hundred through chance alone. One may therefore consider this as probably a significant difference, and vitamin C supplements to the diet may therefore be judged to give a slight advantage in reducing the number of colds experienced.”

The next sentence in their report is, “However, one may well question the practical importance of such a difference.”

Drs. Cowan, Diehl and Baker did not consider their observed 15 per cent decrease in the incidence of colds in their vitamin C subjects to be important enough to justify mention in their summary. I consider it—and similar statistically significant observations reported by other investigators—to be important. It is on this matter of judgment, not of fact, that Dr. Diehl and I differ.

Dr. Diehl also states in his letter that I had failed to mention a later report by him and one of his two earlier co-workers. I had, in fact, referred to it, although not by name, in the following sentences: “In the book I discuss also three careful studies that gave negative results. In two of these studies the patients were given ascorbic acid for three days only, beginning after the cold had been contracted. ... No protective effect was observed under these conditions.” The study reported in 1950 by Drs. Cowan and Diehl is one of the two three-day studies.

LINUS PAULING

Stanford, Calif., Jan. 4, 1971

¹ Diehl HS (1970-12-26) Vitamin C: Cure for Cold?

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